
Deliverable D-JRP21-WP6.28

Workpackage 6

Responsible partners: VFL/EMU, BfR,
APHA, IZSLER, AGES

Contributing partners: SVA, VRI, ISS

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018 (BIOPIGEE 01/01/2020)
Duration	60 Months (BIOPIGEE 30 Months, requested extension for 6 additional months)

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

JIP/JRP deliverable	D-JRP21-WP6.28 Workshop 4 completed
Project Acronym	BIOPIGEE
Author	Tarmo Niine (EMU), Arvo Viltrop (EMU), Richard Smith (APHA), Elke Burow (BfR)
Other contributors	Task participants from: BfR, SVA, APHA, AGES, IZSLER, ISS
Due month of the report	- (additional workshop and deliverable)
Actual submission month	58
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R Save date: 10-Oct-22
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input type="checkbox"/> WHO <input type="checkbox"/> OIE <input type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s): Social Media:
	Other recipient(s): via Zenodo

BIOPIGEE

Workshop 4 completed

Participating institutes (in the workshop organisation)

VFL/EMU, APHA, IZSLER, BfR

Further contributing institutes

AGES, VRI, SVA

Background and objective

The workshop was originally planned to take place as whole day event in conjunction to a relevant conference in order to disseminate preliminary results from the BIOPIGEE project and to gain further insight into BIOPIGEE studies according to input from stakeholders. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the implementation of the event was delayed and changed to an online format, also split into two different workshops, one on primary production, and one on slaughterhouse biosecurity practice which this report covers. For the workshop on slaughterhouse biosecurity, stakeholders of slaughterhouses, veterinary surveillance, meat inspection and academia were invited. The objective of this online workshop was to share and discuss evidence of identified effectiveness of biosecurity measures from the BIOPIGEE project and further possible implementation of these measures in practice with stakeholders (e.g. meat inspectors, industry bodies, slaughterhouse personnel responsible for biosecurity, farming counsellors and veterinarians).

BIOPIGEE project

The zoonotic pathogens *Salmonella* and hepatitis E virus can cause acute and chronic diseases in humans. The most common transmission route is assumed to be foodborne from pigs. The aim of the project BIOPIGEE “biosecurity practices for pig farming across Europe” of the One Health European Joint Programme is to identify effective and cost-efficient biosecurity measures for the reduction of these pathogens in the pig production chain in order to prevent human infections. To achieve this, different literature reviews, field studies, experiments and transmission/cost modelling are carried out. Finally, it is the aim to inform stakeholders like farmers, veterinarians, authorities and the pig industry about the findings on best biosecurity practice.

Invitation

The invitation, as follows below, was sent by task members to professionals through emailing lists to professionals such as slaughterhouse personnel, pig breeding associations, industrial experts, governmental and non-governmental staff, researchers and scientists on 8th August 2022 by email. A reminder was sent on 31st August 2022. The BIOPIGEE project group was informed about the upcoming

workshop and repeatedly reminded. A link to the web tool (Microsoft Teams) where the meeting was hosted, organised by EMU, was sent to the participants with a registration link in the invitation.

Invitation

Workshop programme

One Health EJP - BIOPIGEE

Date / Time	16 th September 2022 / 10:00 – 12:00 CET
Venue	Online Workshop, organised by BIOPIGEE WP6
Meeting	Biosecurity Measures in Slaughterhouses to Control Salmonella and Hepatitis E virus
Room	Hosted by the Estonian University of Life Science (EMU) in MS Teams

Biosecurity Measures in Slaughterhouses to Control *Salmonella* and Hepatitis E Virus (HEV)

BIOPIGEE Online Workshop 16th September 2022; 10:00-12:00

Salmonella and hepatitis E virus (HEV) are zoonotic pathogens that can lead to subclinical infections in pigs, and cause gastrointestinal infections in humans through the food chain. Biosecurity protocols are important tools for identifying optimal and suboptimal practices in pig slaughterhouses related to the introduction and transmission of infectious pathogens, and can thus help control the occurrence and spread of Salmonella and HEV.

A European consortium known as the BIOPIGEE project ('Biosecurity practices for pig farming across Europe') has since 2020 conducted research to identify the most effective biosecurity practices that limit the occurrence and spread of Salmonella and HEV in pigs.

One aspect of the project has been to assess the scientific evidence on the effectiveness of biosecurity measures applied in slaughterhouses to reduce the microbial contamination of pig carcasses. Based on information obtained from scientific literature, a questionnaire study was designed to investigate if and how widely these biosecurity measures are applied in slaughterhouses of participating European countries.

The results of the BIOPIGEE project on slaughterhouse biosecurity measures will be presented by project participants during the workshop and opportunity will be given to discuss these results to all workshop attendance. Specialists in the field of slaughter hygiene of pigs, both from the slaughterhouse industry and from the surveillance authorities, as well as any other interested parties are invited to participate.

This meeting is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

Microsoft Teams meeting

Join on your computer or mobile app

[Click here to join the meeting](#)

Or join by entering a meeting ID

Meeting ID: 390 979 950 27

Passcode: WKr5c7

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

Invitation poster (created by Elaine Campling e.campling@surrey.ac.uk)

Save the Date!
One Health EJP
OHEJP BIOPIGEE Project Workshop:
Biosecurity Measures in Slaughterhouses
to Control *Salmonella*

Date: 10-12am CEST, 16th September, 2022

Location: Online

Audience: Animal slaughterhouse and processing companies, food standard regulatory authorities, researchers working within food safety, and those interested in biosecurity measures to control *Salmonella* and hepatitis E in slaughterhouses

Registration: [here](#)

@OneHealthEJP

ONE Health EJP

#OneHealthEJP #OHEJPBIOPIGEE #StrongerTogether

Program

The program was in two sessions (see below). The first session was about biosecurity measures in slaughterhouse against *Salmonella*. Second session focused on hepatitis E virus in general and in slaughterhouses. Both sessions were followed by discussion, where participants were able to ask questions from the presenters. Chat questions are presented below.

Chair/Chat: APHA/Richard Smith- Chat/Notes: BfR/Elke Burow

1. Session – Control of Salmonella in Slaughterhouses

10:00-10:05	Introduction (EMU/ Arvo Viltrop, BfR/ Niels Bandick)
10:05-10:35	Literature Overview (Guidance Document) and Discussion (EMU/Arvo Viltrop)
10:35-11:05	Survey Results on the Implementation of Biosecurity Measures in Slaughterhouses of BIOPIGEE Partner Countries (EMU/ Tarmo Niine)
11:05-11:10	<i>Short break</i>

Chair/Chat: EMU/ Arvo Viltrop- Chat/Notes: AGES/Elena Sassu

2. Session – Control of other pathogens incl. hepatitis E virus in slaughterhouses

11:10-11:20	Hepatitis E Virus (BfR/Nadine Althof)
11:20-11:40	Results on Environmental Sampling at Slaughterhouses (IZSLER/Enrico Pavoni)
11:40-12:00	Questions & discussion
12:00	<i>Closing of the workshop</i>

Participants

In total, 138 participants registered to the online workshop and there were 202 views of the registration page. Finally, there were 79 participants taking part of the meeting, from whom 10 participated in the BIOPIGEE project.

Number of participants by country and employment

Country	Academic	Government bodies	Industry bodies	NGOs	Grand Total
Austria		1			1
Estonia	4	12	2		18
Ethiopia	1				1
France	1		1		2
Germany		4	6		10
India				1	1
Italia		1			1
Italy		3			3
Jordania				1	1
Latvia		2			2
Liberia				1	1
Netherlands	1	6	1		8
Nigeria				1	1
Pakistan	1				1
Romania		1			1
Spain	1				1
Sweden		2			2
UK	2	13	9		24
Grand Total	11	45	19	4	79

The Workshop

The workshop was conducted according to the planned program. The first session presentation gave an overview of effective control measures found in published scientific literature on *Salmonella* contamination at slaughterhouses. The second presentation discussed results found from a survey carried out in BIOPIGEE T2.3 task partnering countries.

The second session's first presentation focused on hepatitis E virus infection and epidemiology, also giving an overview of current state-of-the-art knowledge on the virus in general. The second presentation also presented results from a study, where three different abattoirs' slaughter lines were sampled.

After each talk participants had the opportunity to ask questions to presenters and at the end of the second session there was a lively discussion with presenters and the audience.

Comments collection during the workshop

Chat questions (deleted names and times)

Do you have a view on how singeing might affect spore-forming bacteria?

via the process scald temperature was mentioned and singing. Is the dehairing process not a key point in salmonella? have the studies demonstrated that reduction in surface hair before singing allowing the heat to remove from the pore

What single change in current European practices do you think would achieve the greatest reduction in consumer exposure to Salmonella via pig products?

Can you say anything about the quality of the studies - as we have seen in the review of measures for primary production, the quality lacked sometimes - is it better for slaughterhouse published studies?

The presentation mentioned scald temps and singing but not the dehairing processes. Have studies demonstrated that reduction in hair in the process before singing has a greater positive effect in reduction of salmonella. theory is reduction of hair would allow the singe to reduce salmonella welled in the pore ?

Thank you for the wonderful presentation

What does N/A mean for the surface sampling?

Under EU law you are not allowed to wash fecal contamination.

was the micro data from those in the questionnaire requested alongside this questionnaire to assess BSM effectiveness?

please publish not only in scientific papers but also for practitioners

Possible technical differences between European slaughterhouses - can you say anything on this?

Conclusion

The workshop gave a very good, up to date overview on discussed topics: *Salmonella* contamination in slaughterhouse and hepatitis E virus in pigs.

Future work

Publications on effective biosecurity measures for slaughterhouse, and on the survey of the implementation of best practices in slaughterhouses and sampling of slaughterlines are in process and will be published in the near future. These publications presenting relevant results will be distributed to stakeholders.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.